

RAMAN SPECTRA OF SOME COMPLEX HALIDES OF MERCURY

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Raman spectral evidence has been obtained for the existence of HgCl_4^0 ion in addition to that for the molecule or ion like HgCl_2 and HgCl_4^+ .

Compounds of the type K_2HgCl_4 giving rise to the ion HgCl_4^+ are well known. If, however, one molecule of HgCl_2 is mixed with one molecule of KCl we expect to get either (i) a mixture of K_2HgCl_4 and HgCl_2 , or (ii) compound of the type KHgCl_2 , giving rise to the ion HgCl_2^+ . The present work aims at deciding between these two alternatives.

It may, however, be mentioned that the previous workers (Krishnamurti, *Indian J. Phys.*, 1931, 6, 7; Braune and Engelbrecht, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1930, 11B, 409; Bernstein and Martin, *Trans. Roy. Soc. Canada*, 1937, 34, III, 95) favoured the alternative.

The investigation has been extended to the study of the compound of the type $2\text{KBr} \cdot \text{HgCl}_2$ and to the complex compounds formed by HgBr_2 and HgI_2 on the addition corresponding alkali halide.

R E S U L T S

The following table gives Raman frequencies in cm^{-1} and their relative intensities. The exciting radiation is $\lambda 4355 \cdot 34$ of the mercury spectrum. The shifts marked with a single asterisk denote that these have been confirmed by the line obtained by excitation with $\lambda 4046 \cdot 5$ or $\lambda 5461 \cdot 73$, while those marked with double asterisks show that the frequencies have been measured microphotometrically. Aqueous solutions have been used. Of the following notations are also used.

(v. s. = very strong ; s = strong ; m = medium ; w = weak)

Substance.	Authors' data.	Braune & Engelbrecht.	Bernstein & Martin.
HgCl_2 { (crystal)	*320.5 (v. s.)		
{ (soln.)	**330.5 (m)	315-327	
$\frac{1}{2}\text{KCl} \cdot \text{HgCl}_2$ (soln.)	318 (s)		
$\text{KCl} \cdot \text{HgCl}_2$..	**300 (m) 328 (w)		
$\text{HCl} \cdot \text{HgCl}_2$..	304 (m) 331 (w)		265 302
$1\frac{1}{2}\text{KCl} \cdot \text{HgCl}_2$..	273 (m) 300 (m)		
$2\text{KCl} \cdot \text{HgCl}_2$ { (crystal)	273 (m)		
{ (soln.)	*,**274.4 (s)	266	
$2\text{HCl} \cdot \text{HgCl}_2$ (soln.)	273.7 (s)		265
$2\text{KBr} \cdot \text{HgCl}_2$ (soln.)	*178 (v. s.)		
HgBr_2 (crystal)	*193 (v. s.)	187	
$2\text{KBr} \cdot \text{HgBr}_2$ (soln.)	*177 (s)	166	
$2\text{KI} \cdot \text{HgI}_2$..	126 (s)	126	

DISCUSSION

Mercuric Chloride and its Complex Compounds.—The frequency due to HgCl_2 molecule is evidently $\Delta\nu 330$. On the addition of one molecule of KCl or HCl there appears a new line at $\Delta\nu 300$ together with that for HgCl_2 , viz., $\Delta\nu 330$ which is very weak. The new line $\Delta\nu 300$, therefore, seems to be characteristic of HgCl_2' ion.

On further addition of one molecule of KCl or HCl to $\text{KCl} \cdot \text{HgCl}_2$ or $\text{HCl} \cdot \text{HgCl}_2$, the reduced frequency observed above is further reduced to $\Delta\nu 274$, while all the other lines disappear. The line $\Delta\nu 274$ should, therefore, be attributed to HgCl_2'' ion. We thus have the following characteristic frequencies.—

HgCl_2	$\Delta\nu 330 \text{ cm.}^{-1}$
HgCl_2'	300 ,,
HgCl_2''	274 ,,

Although Braune and Engelbrecht worked with five different solutions of composition $0.43\text{KCl} \cdot \text{HgCl}_2$, $0.86\text{KCl} \cdot \text{HgCl}_2$, $1.29\text{KCl} \cdot \text{HgCl}_2$, $2.36\text{KCl} \cdot \text{HgCl}_2$, and $8.6\text{KCl} \cdot \text{HgCl}_2$, the measurement of only one plate has been recorded presumably that corresponding to the last solution containing an over-excess of KCl (8.6 mols. of KCl) and hence giving rise to the most intense Raman line. They apparently took it for granted that the frequency shift of the new line was the same in every plate. If measurements had been made on all the plates they would have arrived at a different conclusion.

Our observations are in qualitative, and in some respects quantitative agreement with those of Bernstein and Martin who noted that "there is a gradual decrease in the frequency

shift of HgCl_2 , as the amount of HCl is increased" (Hibben, "Raman Effect and its Chemical Applications," 1939, p. 459). These authors give 265 for the frequency of $2\text{HCl} \cdot \text{HgCl}_2$, and $\Delta\nu$ 302 for $\text{HCl} \cdot \text{HgCl}_2$. The value 302 agrees excellently with the mean of our results for $\text{KCl} \cdot \text{HgCl}_2$, (300) and $\text{HCl} \cdot \text{HgCl}_2$, (304). The discrepancy between the results for $2\text{KCl} \cdot \text{HgCl}_2$, viz. 265 (their value) and 274 (our value) is to be attributed to the composition of the solutions used. While we employed integral molecular proportions, they employed non-integral ratios of HCl and HgCl_2 . However the difference is only nine units.

Thus while we agree with Braune and Engelbrecht that a solution of HgCl_2 , containing a large excess of KCl (or HCl) gives a single line due to $\text{HgCl}_2^{\prime}$ ion, we entirely disagree with them on the point that the new line given by, say $0.86\text{KCl} \cdot \text{HgCl}_2$, is the same as that given by $2.36\text{KCl} \cdot \text{HgCl}_2$, or $8.6\text{KCl} \cdot \text{HgCl}_2$.

The evidence for the existence of $\text{HgCl}_2^{\prime}$ ion is further furnished by the results obtained from intermediate mixtures such as $\frac{1}{2}\text{KCl} \cdot \text{HgCl}_2$, and $1\frac{1}{2}\text{KCl} \cdot \text{HgCl}_2$.

$\frac{1}{2}\text{KCl} \cdot \text{HgCl}_2$.—This might be regarded as either an equimolecular mixture of HgCl_2 and KHgCl_2 , or a complex compound of the formula KHg_2Cl_3 , or a mixture of K_2HgCl_4 and HgCl_2 , in the ratio of 1 : 3.

The last possibility is ruled out because there is no line corresponding to $\text{HgCl}_2^{\prime}$ ions. The observed shift is $\Delta\nu$ 318 with a width of 24 cm^{-1} . The observed frequency is significantly near the mean of the frequencies 330 and 300, that is of those attributed to HgCl_2 molecule and $\text{HgCl}_2^{\prime}$ ion respectively. The question whether the line is a doublet can only be decided by a microphotograph which it was not possible to take in this particular case.

There is also the second alternative viz., the complex $\text{Hg}_2\text{Cl}_3^{\prime}$ ion. This perhaps should give a more complicated spectrum.

The evidence obtained from $1\frac{1}{2}\text{KCl} \cdot \text{HgCl}_2$, is more convincing.

$1\frac{1}{2}\text{KCl} \cdot \text{HgCl}_2$.—If this was regarded as an equimolecular mixture of KHgCl_2 and K_2HgCl_4 , it should give rise to two lines of $\Delta\nu$ 300 and 274 of equal intensity. This was exactly what was observed. The two lines could be distinguished under the microscope and hence no microphotograph was necessary. Microphotometric records were obtained only for HgCl_2 , $\text{KCl} \cdot \text{HgCl}_2$, and $2\text{KCl} \cdot \text{HgCl}_2$.

Chemical Evidence.—Chemical evidence for the existence of compounds like KHgCl_2 and HHgCl_2 , is not lacking. Crystals of composition HHgCl_2 , were prepared by Davy while the anhydrous salt KHgCl_2 was obtained by Linebarger (Mellor, "Treatise on Inorganic Chemistry", 1923, IV, 848, 856). The existence of compounds like H_2HgCl_4 and K_2HgCl_4 is well known.

$2\text{KBr} \cdot \text{HgCl}_2$.—The shift obtained is $\Delta\nu$ 178, those given by K_2HgBr_4 and K_2HgCl_4 being 172 and 274 respectively. The proximity of the observed shift to that obtained with K_2HgBr_4 , excludes the possibility of considering the substance as a mixture of K_2HgBr_4 and K_2HgCl_4 .^{*} The formation of the compound $\text{K}_2\text{Hg}(\text{ClBr})_2$, is also similarly to be excluded.

$2\text{KBr} \cdot \text{HgBr}_2$, and $2\text{KI} \cdot \text{HgI}_2$.— $2\text{KBr} \cdot \text{HgBr}_2$, and $2\text{KI} \cdot \text{HgI}_2$ give shifts at $\Delta\nu$ 172 and 126 respectively and represent the vibration frequencies of the ions $(\text{HgBr}_2)^{\prime}$ and $(\text{HgI}_2)^{\prime}$. Solutions of the type $\text{KBr} \cdot \text{HgBr}_2$, and $\text{KI} \cdot \text{HgI}_2$, in sufficient concentration could not be prepared and it was not possible to obtain evidence for the formation of the ions of the type $\text{HgBr}_2^{\prime}$ and $\text{HgI}_2^{\prime}$.